

CORRELATION BETWEEN MODELING AND EXPERIMENTS FOR A THERMOPLASTIC PULTRUSION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

To obtain a fundamental understanding of the individual processing parameters and die geometry in a thermoplastic pultrusion process, mathematical models are essential in order to minimize the number of necessary experiments. Hence, models to calculate the temperature and pressure distributions in a thermoplastic composite as it travels through the pultrusion line, as well as a model to calculate the accumulated pulling force, are briefly presented. Predictions of the models are compared to experimental data in terms of composite temperature and pulling force, and the correlations are found to be very good.

KEYWORDS: Modeling, Flow Analysis, Pultrusion, Thermoplastics, Manufacturing.

1. INTRODUCTION

The relative lack of fundamental understanding of the pultrusion process has prompted numerous investigators to attempt to mathematically model the process. Most of the past efforts have been directed towards pultrusion of thermoset-matrix composites, while few researchers have considered the special problems of its intricate thermoplastic equivalent (1-3). Analyses of thermoset and thermoplastic pultrusion processes will obviously have many elements in common. However, an analysis of the latter will not include modeling of cure kinetics but instead such added difficulties as non-Newtonian matrix flow (2,3), matrix melting and solidification, crystallization, viscous dissipation, and probably multiple dies.

Temperature and pressure undisputably are the two most important parameters when processing a thermoplastic composite. Hence, models to predict both temperature and pressure within the

composite as it travels through the pultrusion line are presented. A model to calculate the pulling force of the process is also presented, since it is a particularly easy processing parameter to measure continuously during pultrusion, as well as an excellent indicator of the state of the process.

The set of models presented herein applies to an idealized process at steady state. The models are applied to a heated and a cooled die (see Figure 1) but can easily be applied to any number of dies. In reality, the temperature and pressure distributions are so intricately coupled that an extensive, iterative numerical solution would be required to fully solve the problem. Likewise, the pulling force depends upon both the temperature and pressure distributions in a complicated fashion. Instead of attempting to fully solve this complex set of problems, simplified situations are considered. Hence, the temperature and pressure models treat a two-dimensional geometry with one-dimensional heat transfer and matrix flow, respectively. The pulling force model treats a quasi-three-dimensional situation—a constant-width geometry. The temperature model is assumed independent of the pressure model, and the pressure model is only partially dependent upon the predictions of the temperature model. With the exception of a shear-rate-dependent matrix viscosity and a temperature-dependent matrix density, the properties of fiber, matrix, and composite are assumed constant, i. e. unaffected by changes in temperature, pressure, and fiber volume fraction within each die. However, all properties are allowed to vary from one die to another.

Figure 1. The modeled die system.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODELS

2.1 Temperature Model The temperature model treats a heated and a cooled die separated by an air gap (see Figure 1). The aspect ratio of the die cavities is assumed so large that heat transfer in the y-direction may be neglected. The composite is treated as a (transversely) isotropic material, and it is also assumed that the taper of the heated die may be treated as a constant cross section, and that axial heat conduction, viscous dissipation, and melting and solidification issues are negligible. Hence, throughout the heat transfer analyses the composite is treated as an infinitely long slab of finite height, $2h_L$ (see Figure 1), with either prescribed temperature or prescribed heat flux on the two opposing surfaces, $z = \pm h_L$. Since the composite is moving at a constant speed, U , the time is in the solutions replaced by the x-coordinate, $t = x/U$. Hence, the familiar solution to the prescribed-boundary-temperature problem is

$$T(x,z) = T_{\text{die}}(x) + \frac{2}{h_L} (T_0(z) - T_{\text{die}}(x)) \sum_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{(-1)^n}{\lambda_n} \exp\left(-\lambda_n^2 \frac{\alpha_{\text{TD},z^2}}{U}\right) \cos(\lambda_n z) \right] \quad (1)$$

where

$$\lambda_n = \frac{(2n+1)\pi}{2h_L} \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (2)$$

In the case of a constant-heat-flux boundary condition, i.e. when the composite is exposed to air, the corresponding solution is

$$T(x,z) = T_{\text{air}} + 4 (T_0(z) - T_{\text{air}}) \sum_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{\sin(\lambda_n h_L)}{2\lambda_n h_L + \sin(2\lambda_n h_L)} \exp\left(-\lambda_n^2 \frac{\alpha_{\text{TD},z^2}}{U}\right) \cos(\lambda_n z) \right] \quad (3)$$

where the coefficients λ_n are iteratively obtained from

$$\cot(\lambda_n h_L) = \frac{\lambda_n k_{\text{air}}}{h_c} \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (4)$$

In the equations above, T is the temperature, α_{TD} the thermal diffusivity of the composite, k_{air} the thermal conductivity of the surrounding air, and h_c the coefficient of convective heat transfer. T_0 is the composite temperature upon entry into the die, T_{die} the temperature of the die, and T_{air} the temperature of the surrounding air.

2.2 Pressure Model The pressure model treats the heated (first) die of Figure 1. It is assumed that all fibers in the over-saturated bundle that enters the taper of the die are parallel to the pulling direction and that the matrix flows only along the length of the fibers. Throughout the die the fiber-volume-fraction distribution is assumed transversely isotropic. Due to the assumption that the density of the matrix is allowed to change with temperature only, the matrix pressure build-up within the composite is solely the result of matrix flow relative to the fibers. This matrix flow is caused by the geometric constriction at the entrance of the die, as well as by the thermal expansion of the composite within the confines of the die. The flow is assumed to be independent of the z -coordinate, and it is assumed that there is no matrix flow relative to the fibers at the very end of the die ($x = L_2$). As the temperature of the composite is likely to increase gradually within the die, the thermal expansion must result in matrix flow relative to the fibers, which therefore must be directed towards the entrance of the die. Hence, the matrix flow through a cross section at a coordinate x in the constant-cross-section part of the die may be expressed as

$$q(x) = U(1 - v_L) + \hat{q}(x) = U(1 - v_L) - U\alpha_{\text{TE},Z}(T_{\text{AV}}(L_2) - T_{\text{AV}}(x)) \quad L_1 \leq x \leq L_2 \quad (5)$$

where $q(x)$ is the matrix flow rate per unit area in a die-fixed coordinate system; $\hat{q}(x)$ is the flow rate per unit area in a fiber-fixed coordinate system; v_L is the fiber volume fraction for $x \geq L_1$; α_{TE} is the thermal expansion coefficient of the composite; and T_{AV} is the average temperature of a composite cross section. Taking into account the matrix flow caused by the geometrical

constriction of the taper, as well as that caused by thermal expansion, the matrix flow relative to the fibers within the taper may be written as (3)

$$\hat{q}(x) = q(L_1) \frac{v_f(x)}{v_L} - U(1 - v_f(x)) - U\alpha_{TEZ}(T_{AV}(L_1) - T_{AV}(x)) \quad 0 \leq x \leq L_1 \quad (6)$$

where the fiber-volume-fraction distribution is given by

$$v_f(x) = \frac{v_L}{\frac{v_L}{v_0} + \left(1 - \frac{v_L}{v_0}\right) \frac{x}{L_1}} \quad 0 \leq x \leq L_1 \quad (7)$$

and the flow rate at the end of the taper, $q(L_1)$, is given by Equation (5). Once the matrix flow relative to the fibers is known, a flow-rate–pressure-drop relationship is required to determine the pressure distribution throughout the die. A flow-rate–pressure-drop relationship that has proved convenient to use is the Carreau-model equivalent of Darcy's law (2-3):

$$\frac{dP_m}{dx} = - \frac{4K_0K_1^2\eta_0\hat{q}(x)}{r_f^2} \frac{v_f^2(x)}{(1 - v_f(x))^3} \left[1 + \left(\frac{2K_0K_1\lambda\hat{q}(x)}{r_f} \frac{v_f(x)}{(1 - v_f(x))^2} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (8)$$

where dP_m/dx is the matrix pressure gradient; K_0 is a shape factor depending upon the shape of the cross section of the hypothetical capillaries of the fiber bed; K_1 is the tortuosity, defined as the ratio of the distance traveled by a fluid element and the fiber bed thickness; r_f is the fiber radius; η_0 is the zero–shear-rate viscosity of the matrix; λ is a time constant indicating the shear rate at which shear-thinning effects become important; and n is a dimensionless constant describing the degree of shear thinning.

The total pressure exerted upon a compressed fiber bed impregnated with a fluid is carried by both the fluid and the fibers. One of many equivalent expressions for the load carried by the fiber bed is (4)

$$P_f = C \frac{\sqrt{\frac{v_f(x)}{v_0}} - 1}{\left(\sqrt{\frac{v_\infty}{v_f(x)}} - 1\right)^4} \quad (9)$$

where C is a spring constant, v_0 the fiber volume fraction of the uncompressed fiber bed, and v_∞ the highest fiber volume fraction obtainable. This equation directly gives the distribution of the load carried by the fiber bed in terms of the x -coordinate. Introducing Equations (5) - (7) into Equation (8) enables expressions for the matrix pressure gradient to be obtained in terms of the x -coordinate throughout the die. However, while the matrix–pressure-gradient expression may not be solved with analytical means, numerical integration is trivial.

As the matrix is assumed to have only a temperature-dependent density, the composite will never touch the cooled die, since even an incremental temperature decrease is sufficient to cause thermal contraction. However, in reality (with a non-idealized fluid model) expansion due to stress relaxation may occur upon exit from the heated die, in which case the composite initially may touch

the cooled die causing considerable stresses within the composite. Such considerations are beyond the scope of this treatment.

2.3 Pulling Force Model The predictions of the pressure model may be used as input for the pulling force model. This model treats a die cavity of local taper angle β , $0 \leq \beta < 90^\circ$ (see Figure 1). The total pulling force required to pull a composite through a die is

$$F = \int f(x) dA(x) \quad (10)$$

where f is the resisting force per unit area of the composite in contact with the die and A the internal surface area of the die. The resistance is assumed to have three contributing factors: viscous, compaction, and friction resistance. For the viscous resistance it is assumed that a neat matrix boundary layer acts as a lubricant between the outermost layer of fibers and the die wall, with no slip conditions at both interfaces. The force per unit area required to pull the composite at a constant speed is equal to the shear stress, which is assumed constant throughout the thickness of the boundary layer. Hence, for a Carreau fluid the viscous resistance is

$$f_v = \eta_0 \frac{U}{\delta} \left(1 + \left(\frac{\lambda U}{\delta} \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \cos\beta \quad (11)$$

For this expression to be useful, an estimate of the thickness of the boundary layer, δ , is required, and it is assumed to be equal to the shortest distance between fibers within the composite, which for a regular, triangular arrangement equals

$$\delta = r_f \left(\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3} v_f}} - 2 \right) \quad (12)$$

The compaction resistance consists of two parts, as the total load supported by the die equals the combined values of the matrix pressure and the load carried by the fiber bed. Hence, the resistance from compaction is

$$f_c = (P_m + P_f \cos\beta) \sin\beta \quad (13)$$

This contribution vanishes when the taper angle is zero, since for a constant cross section die there is no further compaction. The friction resistance is that which occurs where bare fibers touch the die wall without a lubricating matrix boundary layer in between, and it may be written as

$$f_f = P_f \mu \cos^2\beta \quad (14)$$

where μ is the friction coefficient. Considering the die assembly shown in Figure 1 and assuming that the width of the dies is constant and equal to $2w$, the total pulling force may be expressed as

$$F_{\text{tot}} = 4 \cdot \int_0^{l_2} f_{\text{tot}}(x) \cdot \{w + h(x)\} dx \quad (15)$$

since, with the current fluid model, the composite will never touch the cooled die. The total resisting force per unit area according to the above discussion is

$$f_{\text{tot}} = (1 - f) f_v + f_c + f f_f \quad (16)$$

where f denotes the fraction of the composite perimeter that is subject to friction. Hence, the fraction that is subject to viscous resistance must be $1 - f$.

3. COMPARISON BETWEEN MODELING AND EXPERIMENTS

To verify the models presented above, a pultrusion line was built exclusively for manufacturing thermoplastic-matrix composites (5). During experiments, relevant process parameters are recorded by a data acquisition and control facility, which allows for continuous monitoring of temperature, pressure, and pulling force, as well as digital control of pulling speed (5). The temperatures and pressures within the composite are measured by disposable thermocouples and force-sensing resistors, respectively, that are fed into the die together with the prepregs and thereupon molded into the composite. The pulling force is continuously measured by a load cell that measures the resistance of the dies. When this paper was prepared, no pressure measurements had yet been attempted.

The material used in the experiments presented below was 6.4 mm wide tows of carbon fibers melt impregnated with polyether etherketone (PEEK), molded into composites with a rectangular cross section of 3.2 x 6.4 mm.

3.1 Temperature Two experimentally measured temperature distributions are shown in Figures 2 and 3 together with predictions from the temperature model outlined above. The final locations of the thermocouples in the composite cross sections are shown in the upper right-hand corner of the figures, and the locations of the pultrusion dies are shown at the bottom. The temperature set points were 300°C for the preheater, 380°C for the heated die, and 100°C for the cooled die. The pulling speeds were 2 and 4 mm/s, respectively.

Figure 2. Composite temperature as a function of position in pultrusion line at a pulling speed of 2 mm/s. Comparison between predictions and experimental data.

Figure 3. Composite temperature as a function of position in pultrusion line at a pulling speed of 4 mm/s. Comparison between predictions and experimental data.

3.2 Pulling Force Figure 4 shows the pulling force as a function of pulling speed. The data points were obtained from experimental runs where both the preheater and the heated die were set to 380°C and the cooled die to 100°C. The lower set of data points (unfilled symbols) is from an experimental run where the (heated) die was just slightly over-filled, i. e. virtually no material was squeezed back in the taper, while the higher set of data points (filled symbols) is from a run where the die was highly over-filled, i. e. large amounts of material were squeezed back. In both cases the fiber volume fraction was increased from 0.55 to 0.60 from the prepreg to the composite, so the pressures and pulling forces predicted by the models are the same. The dashed line represents the original predictions; the solid lines represent adjusted predictions that are explained in the next section.

Figure 4. Pulling force as a function of pulling speed. Comparison between measurements and predictions.

4. DISCUSSION

The predicted temperature profiles of Figures 2 and 3 have been fitted to the experimental data using a value of the thermal diffusivity 17 percent lower than that reported in reference (6). This enables a good correlation between experiments and predictions to be obtained, especially at the higher of the two pulling speeds (see Figure 3). However, in both cases the experimental data indicate that higher temperatures are recorded within the composite than in the heated die itself. One reason for this discrepancy may be viscous dissipation, which is not included in the modeling.

The pulling force data points of Figure 4 were obtained from runs where the preheater and the heated die were set to the same temperature, thereby cancelling thermal-expansion-induced contributions to the pulling force, since the thermal-expansion terms of Equations (5) and (6) in this case are zero. The dashed line at the bottom of Figure 4 represents the original predictions of the pulling force model. As the line suggests, the model predicts that even an infinitesimal pulling force would start the process. However, liquids containing large amounts of solids tend to have a yield stress (7), which the pulling force model does not account for. Assuming that the highly fiber-filled matrix has a yield stress, the original predictions can be shifted to coincide with the data from the slightly over-filled die. Based on the 4-mm/s data point, this yield stress translates into a minimum pulling force of 715 N required to start the process.

From the pulling force calculations, which are based on a fiber-volume-fraction increase from 0.55 to 0.60, i. e. the dashed line in Figure 4, one finds that the contributions from friction and compaction are negligible. Hence, virtually all the resistance is of a viscous nature. It is obvious that any frictional contributions from the heated die must be very small since the fiber-volume-fraction increase is small (see Equations (9) and (14)). In theory, a fiber-volume-fraction increase from 0.55 to 0.60 translates into insignificant matrix back flow in the taper unless the taper angle is very small or the run long enough to accumulate a lot of material in the taper (see Equation (6)). Therefore, since also the fiber-volume-fraction increase is small, the compaction contribution to the pulling force is negligible (see Equations (8) and (13)). Since the slightly over-filled die most closely corresponds to the models, this explains why the correlation with the data from this experiment is so good.

On the other hand, in the case of the highly over-filled die where a large amount of material was accumulated in the taper, there obviously must have been significant matrix back flow over a greater taper length than indicated by the fiber-volume-fraction increase. Hence, by using the same yield stress as for the data from the slightly over-filled die, one can find a quite realistic taper length to give the predicted line shown in Figure 4. By using this taper length in the predictions, one finds that in this case the compaction is the clearly dominant contribution to the pulling force, which explains the different slopes of the two sets of experimental data and predictions. Not surprisingly, it is therefore advantageous to have as little over-filling of the die as possible to keep the pulling force at reasonably low levels.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Models to predict temperature and pressure distributions within the composite as it moves through the pultrusion line, as well as a model to predict the pulling force from the die system, have been presented. The temperature model is found to agree well with experimental data for different positions within the composite, as well as for data obtained at different pulling speeds. The pulling force model agrees very well with experimental data at a variety of pulling speeds and for both viscous and compaction-dominated situations. These promising correlations between predictions and experimental data indicate the soundness of the proposed models.

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BIOGRAPHIES

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